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E-Palli LLC

Address: 2055 Limestone Rd Ste 200C, Zip Code: 19808,
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Email: ajebe@e-palli.com

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Necessity Development Factor of Computerisation in Madras High Court for E-Govern and E-Court

B. Swamynathan¹

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ABSTRACT

The Government of India ICT has been instrumental in computerizing all sectors of the country. For the effective administration of Madras High Court, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) was applied in its judicial activities. It will speed case receiving and cases delivering without delay and hesitations, manual work would be considered as a secondary work, and importance would be given to e-governance to dispense cases easily and quickly and provide judgments rapidly. Delay in providing justice is delaying in living meaningful life and discipline life, without delay cases and judgments would be delivered rapidly as per the expectations and waiting of the petitioners through the e-governance method. Human being used to getting tired though they have been given their actual duty by the authority they will not do that on account of job satisfaction and security, by these justices are not dispatched and rendered quickly owing to the officer's manual work thereby petitioners will get unbelief and dissatisfaction on government as well as judicial. This article discusses the steps taken to computerize the High court and the need to expedite them.

INTRODUCTION

During the manual work period, petitioners had been asked bribes and Commissions to complete their cases by the court officers, it has been influencing in justices are delayed and people are getting back from seeking the judiciary help. To avoid and neglect all these corruptions and malpractices in the judiciary campus and compartment e-governance system was introduced in July 2016 with the interest and purpose to receive cases easily, quickly and render justices rapidly by this following social problems would be resolved and rectified and also prevented beforehand.

Criminals would arrest based on the rendered judgments. The affected person's family would be protected from the fear of criminals. Petitioner's frustration on Court would be eliminated. Confidentiality and trust of the petitioners on Court would fortify. The name of the Court would be popularized by providing quality and rapid justice. Peace and progress will be fostered in society by rapid court justices. Criminalized civil society would be cleaned and kept neatly by providing computerized court administrations. Social, political and economic justice would reincarnate and resuscitate by providing speedy justice and pathetic situations of the people would be eliminated.

Liberalism and freedom could be followed by the people in their life by being of the active judiciary. People fearing to police, government officers, rulers, administrators and criminals would be entirely uprooted by rendering computerized rapid justices. Justice is good for a good person and bad for a bad person even providing judgment

to punish one criminal also would be considered as justice and the same justice providing for an innocent person also would be considered as justice. Criminals would be disheartened in terms of thinking to threaten, kill, and intimidated other persons in the social system. Judiciary is up from all the sections of the administration with an intense to punish culprits, robbery person, theft, murderess, criminals, tyranny rulers and exploitations. Judiciary is the uppermost guardian of the people's life, freedom and rights because the rest of the authorities are not guaranteed and believable, all of them will change according to time and money but the judiciary is never and not like that. Towards make strong ethics, morality, disciplined life and decent behaviours at human being harts the computerized judiciary system provides rapidly justices.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Necessity and Requirement of Computer Equipment

The small gap of providing late justice will lead to happen a thousand crimes in India for avoiding this factor computerized administrations is important and made well. The impact of late or delayed justice will encourage all the political and social criminals to do more crimes in poor people living places. The rapid justice system will curb and punish so many wrongdoers and culprits while the delayed justice system is encouraging culprits to commit more criminal activities. Toward make reforms and corrections in political, social, economic, department's judiciary's computerized systems and procedures are most needed one for make a strong

¹ Ph.D., Research Scholar, Department of Political Science & Public Administration, Annamalai University, Tamilnadu, India
* Corresponding author's email: tsiswamynathan@gmail.com

disciplined society including all the above said domains. Judiciary is the highest body because it is a selfless and corrupt-free mechanism, is for the welfare of the people than other government bodies from rulers to people.

In the above-narrated aspects following computerized privileges are rendered to Madras High Court to deliver justice for stagnated cases and also render for fresh cases at a computer speed. The infrastructure of the Chennai High court was facilitated by the computer program. The Hon'ble Judges of the High Court was facilitated with computers with the latest modern configurations. Along with high-speed configurations, computers laptops were provided to each officer and kept in the cabin of the Court offices. The government of Tamilnadu has provided madras High Court branded and quality laptops like Dell and Lenovo with printers systems.

To know all the social and international information of both civil and criminal issues government is provided - Apple i-pads, this i-pad would be helpful to comprehend all the news and information quickly. Apart from these facilities to read and go through today's relevant academic and other social issues online journals systems were commenced, in the court chambers two-line landline telephone system was installed along with internet facilities for complete all the cases information and details, to speed up case processing systems multifunctional software devices were installed in chambers of the courting the chambers of the senior judges' wide broadband internet connections were arranged

Internet Facilities Were Provided to the Registrars

To accelerate court activities all the registrars were given modern types of Laptops and computers along with broadband internet service and connectivity Registry - All the sections of the Registry have been provided with desktop computers interconnected through LAN. Through this system, necessary and needful computers were given to the registrar to type and store all the core issues and matters for future references. To entertain all the petitioners in the court cabins and receptions hall computers are installed with internet facilities to encourage suitors to file a case about their needs in the court.

For speedy data storage and keeping records in the computers government of Tamilnadu has given a High-speed server with software facilities for effective court proceedings. 11 nos. of High-End scanners have been installed in various Judicial and Administrative sections thereby enabling the Madras High Court to Scan and digitize all the current cases being filed and the administrative files thus heralding the era of Digitization. To avoid Xerox and scanning time for judges and officers government has arranged computers and laptop facilities in each section with Xerox and scanning facilities thereby they can minimize their Xerox and scanning time outside and also perform court duties so speedily.

To reduce travel and court time to go to see other court issues and official functions the video conferencing facilities are arranged between Madurai High Court

and Chennai High Court, this system will reduce the unnecessary time which happens when judges to concerned places.

Software Modules

To deal with civil, criminal cases the software modules were installed in the Chennai high court's building which was developed by NIC and entire software facilities and arrangements are done perfectly by the software team. Through best software modules systems, the large cases communication facilities are created by NIC authority and also keep maintaining computer record room by storing all the latest and old versions access are kept into the computers. In this way, they are preparing and storing daily cases and justice's delivery details for the sack of the court achievements. Since received cases, its process are monitored and watch by the computers operators in serial wise this job can do by him since there have been fixed computerized facilities.

Regarding bail granting, interim bail granting, information of the cases, evidence of the cases and witnesses are kept in the computer according to serial and year and date wise. Entirely cases record, date, year, proceeding numbers, names of the petitioners and advocates with judges are enlisted and maintained in the computerized administrative procedure.

The chief meaning of the module's software is nothing but it is a meaning of paperless administrative work system and paperless judicature work all work will be done through computers and technological way with the fast process without delay. This system has been introduced at its subordinate and lower courts also for the sack of administrative perfectness and developments, its goal is to provide all the needs to be justice-seekers from all sections of the people within a stipulated period and time without too much delay. Through these computerized module software systems, the high court of Tamilnadu has been shifted from old manual work to new technological works. In this way it can computerized attendance maintenance system, savings of the personal information's of the judicial officers and staffs, family profile, occupation details of the staff members are stored and entered in the computers, sincerely following biometric entry system, even giving leave letters and asking permission letters are also done through the computerized system. Lodging complaints on any staff will be recorded and all the judiciary regarding issues and cases are to be filed in a computerized way.

So far we rendered services and justices of the high court of Tamilnadu is recorded in the computer properly, all the RTI filed a case and received complaints and evidence of its also recorded and loaded in a computer for the evidence of future years. Visitors records, entry, issuing a pass to court visitors, law college people, along with their college name and years are registered in the computers, purpose of pay visit judiciary, and ID card of the concern students also is recorded and saved at computers to see whenever it require in future for a good purpose and negative purpose.

Regarding duties are given to staff and advocates of the Tamilnadu high Court is also registered on the computers, calling staffs and registrars to assembly in court hall for an urgent meeting will be also Registered in a computer, properly incoming members images, purposes, goal, aim, needs are monitored by the surveillance camera by this court and Hon'ble Judges records achievements, victory in their career, educations, services and occupations and salaries everything would be maintained in the computer properly.

Towards recruiting court staff, officers and Judges would be done through a computerized way, through this system name, calling letters after screening their profile and selections would be done through the computer system.

1. Giving advertisement
2. Receiving applications
3. Screening the received applications
4. Sending selected candidates list for interview

Giving all the rudimentary details of where and how to attend the interview will be notified on the websites of the Court. Here, all types of malpractices, corruption, bias, favouritism and error would be avoided since it has been done by the computerized system.

Digitization of Court Case Records

From July 2016 onwards Tamilnadu High Court will be commenced or began to start to function with computerized and digitalized ways along with so many systematic approaches such as cases, records, files, profiles of the staffs and Hon'ble Judges, Judiciary trials, Judgment day, Record numbers, Petitioner's name, Case details, history, Criminal cases, Civil cases, scanning, typing, Xerox copies, listed cases and all type of cases would be thoroughly filled and recorded in the computers as it can revive and seen in the future for the court evidence.

Digitization of Old/Disposed Case Records

To upload and insert into the computers the case which is recorded before the computer period will be typed neatly and saved into the computers without any mistakes and plunder. All the case sheets, records, files, Judgments sheets and other relevant information would be typed to upload into the computers to revive and revise cases for the present case very dictions as evidence of the justice rendering. These are the cases that would be recorded in the computers, further apart from the court cases regarding court rehabilitation works, renovations works, tendering orders, tender nonelectrical works, tender, floor reformation and relocation work, painting tender, wages, hired employees, electrical, phone bill, utility expenditures, additional court maintenance expenditure, petrol allowances, daily wages, vehicle rearing, food expenditures, party expenditures, repairing works, overhauling works and other court maintenance works and recorded would be uploaded into the computers with years and month for the auditing and accounting purposes.

From the old stage to the present stage the High Court of Tamilnadu has been transferred and shifted with a lot of

reformative attempts and programmes by the initiative of the then was Honourable Judges and Ministers. Herewith the following changes and new programmes and facilities are arranged to improve the architecture and interior infrastructures of the Chennai High Court.

Electrical equipments are installed, to secure and safe the Chennai High Court, Tamilnadu government has fixed fire signals, CCTV camera installations, Digitalized computers are fixed, Gyp board false ceiling is established, modern glass doors are fixed, repository cupboard is arranged, to keep computers suitable long and high tables are arranged, the digitalized training room was established.

CONCLUSION

Central and State Governments must take some actions to make the people aware of the e-Governance and E-Court activities. In view to enlarge Tamilnadu High Court Judiciary and Tamilnadu all the needful, requirements are done to modernize, regularize, systematize, increase court profile and rehabilitate. By allotting sufficient funds to computerize, modernize, rehabilitate and reform the court administration the sufficient efforts are bone even still now. So, further, necessary and thoughtful reformative works should be done in the forthcoming days, for which government and judges are needed to pursue comprehensive reformative work. Computerized system in the court is much good work for completing all the bending and fresh courts in high speed and ultra-speed toward complete all the backblock cases for accomplishing social justice through the legal proceedings. The computerization of the judiciary will make justice available to the people more quickly, and the computerization of the High Courts will be necessary over time to ensure transparency and simplicity.

REFERENCES

- Barber, Sotirios A. 1993. *The Constitution of Judicial Power*. Baltimore: John Hopkins University Press.
- Bardhan, Pranab. 2005. "Nature of Opposition to Economic Reforms in India." *Economic and Political Weekly*, 40:48 (November 26-December 2).
- Batra, J.L. 1997. "Liberalization: Challenge of Change," in *Liberalization: Economic Challenges*. S.K. Srivastava and A.P. Gupta eds. New Delhi: Anmol Publications Pvt. Ltd., pp. 1-11.
- Baxi, Upendra. 1967. "The Little Done, The Vast Undone" -Some Reflections on Reading Granville Austin's." *Journal of Indian Law Institute*, 9, pp. 323-430.
- Baxi, Upendra. 1980. *The Indian Supreme Court and Politics*. Lucknow: Eastern Book Co.
- Baxi, Upendra. 1982. *The Crisis of the Indian Legal System*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House.
- Baxi, Upendra. 1982. "Who Bothers about Supreme Court? The Problem of Impact of Judicial Decisions." *Journal of the Indian Law Institute*, 24:4, pp. 848-62.
- Baxi, Upendra. 1985. *Courage, Craft and Contentions The Indian Supreme Court in the Eighties*. Bombay: Tripathy.

- Baxi, Upendra. 1986. *Towards A Sociology of Indian Law*. Delhi: Satvahan.
- Baxi, Upendra. 1991. "Constitutional Perspectives on Privatization A Footnote to Dalip Swamy." *Mainstream*, July, pp. 3.
- Baxi, Upendra. 1992. "The Recovery of Fire: Nehru and Legitimizing of Power in India," in Nehru and the Indian Constitution. Rajeev Dhavan and Thomas Paul eds. Bombay: Tripathi.
- Baxi, Upendra. 1993. "Judicial Discourse: Dialectics of the Face and Masks." *Journal of Indian Law Institute*, 35:1-2, pp. 1-12.
- Baxi, Upendra. 1993. *Marx and Justice*. Bombay: Tripathi.
- Baxi, Upendra. 1995. "Life of Law Amidst Globalization." *50th Anniversary Conference Australian Law Teachers' Association Cross Currents; Internationalism, National Identity and Law*.
- Baxi, Upendra. 2000. "Constitutionalism as a Site of State Formative Practices." *Cardozo Law Review*, 21:4, pp. 1183-210.
- Beard, Charles. 1967. *The Economic Interpretation of the Constitution of the United States*. New York: Mac Millan.
- Beck, Thorsten, Asli Demirguc-Kunt, and Ross Levine. 2003. "Law, Endowments, and Finance." *Journal of Financial Economics*, 70:2, pp. 137-81.
- Beck, Thorsten, Ross Levine, and Asli Demirguc-Kunt. 2003. "Law and Finance: Why Does Legal Origin Matter? ." *Journal of Comparative Economics*, 31:4, pp. 653-75.
- Bell, John. 1985. *Policy Arguments in Judicial Decisions*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Bell, John. 1987. "The Judge as a Bureaucrat," in Oxford Essay in Jurisprudence. John Eekelaar and John Bell eds. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Besley, Timothy and Rob Burgess. 2002. *Can Labour Regulation Hinder Economic Performance? Evidence from India*. London: London School of Economics: Development Economics Discussion
- Barber, N.W. 2001. "Prelude to the Separation of Powers." *Cambridge Law Journal*, 60:1, pp. 59-88